
Heart Disease Prediction Using Machine Learning Algorithms A Comparative Study

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Abstract:

According to estimates, heart-related illnesses account for around one-third of all deaths globally that makes heart disease to the leading cause of death. Acute coronary syndrome (ACS) and coronary heart disease (CHD). [2] Obesity, tobacco high blood pressure, and cholesterol use are all contributing factors to the rising death rate. [3] Predicting heart disease accurately is essential for early treatment and lowering the death rate. [4] Clinical decision-making can benefit from the application of machine learning (ML). In order to predict the 1-year mortality rate following heart transplantation (HT) in adults with congenital heart disease, we have created a machine learning model. [5] This study suggests to make more accurate predictions using machine learning algorithm on heart disease. Furthermore, machine learning models' performance is evaluated using Accuracy, F1-Measure, Precision, and Recall. [4] The data set can be subjected to several supervised machine learning model types. [6] Our goal was to create a machine learning model for the prediction of heart disease. Additionally, the most realistic model is used to create user-friendly mobile apps and user-friendly online apps. [4]

Index Terms: Heart disease, supervised machine learning, Accuracy, F1-Measure, Precision, and Recall, Machine Learning, Prediction Model, Healthcare, Data Analysis.

Introduction:

The heart is the vital organ in human body. Changes in life can lead to a number of illnesses, such as diabetes, high blood pressure, etc. In the same way, heart failure is a terrible illness. Heart failure is a dangerous illness. [7] Effective treatment and prevention of cardiac disorders depend on early identification, which is a major worldwide health concern. These days, heart disease is one of the most serious conditions that kills the majority of patients. Heart disease is very challenging to diagnose medically. This diagnosis is a difficult procedure that calls for precision and effectiveness. Early revelation of heart disease will reduce the risk of mortality. [8] Elevated blood pressure, which has a major influence on cardiovascular disorders, is

referred to as hypertension. [9] [10] In recent years, revealing the heart disease has emerged as one of the most challenging medical tasks. To find the best predictors of these diseases, researchers examined a number of closely related characteristics. [8] To more accurately identify heart-related conditions, a variety of supervised and unsupervised learning techniques are suggested. [11] The major purpose of computer science's Artificial Intelligence (AI) is to increase computers' intelligence. Since learning is the most fundamental component of intelligence, machine learning (ML) emerged as an area of AI. One of the AI subfields that is developing the fastest is machine learning (ML), which finds application in many facets of life, chiefly in the medical profession. Since ML is an

exceptional and faster tool for data analysis and the medical profession is full with data, it offers a lot of value in the healthcare industry.[12] By examining a variety of medical data, machine learning algorithms have demonstrated significance in the revelation of cardiac disorders. In this study, the presence of cardiac anomalies is detected using Machine Learning (ML) approaches. The suggested approach uses various ML algorithm techniques to classify a risk level of patient and predict the likelihood of heart disease.[8], [13] Computational statistics, which concentrate on applying mathematical optimization to provide methods, theory, and application domains to address real-world corporate, social, industrial, and medical issues, is closely related to machine learning. It falls under two categories Supervised learning and unsupervised learning. In supervised learning, the algorithm uses a set of data that includes the inputs and the intended outputs to create a mathematical model. Unsupervised learning, on the other hand, uses a set of data with only inputs and no desired output labels to create a mathematical model. This work used supervised machine learning to predict cardiac disease using the Classification and Regression Tree (CART) algorithm.[1], [14], [15] A popular area of data science is machine learning, which is a subfield of artificial intelligence research [2]. To determine the relative relevance of each input characteristic, we have employed the Principle Component Analysis (PCA) method to convert the higher dimensional feature space into a lower dimension subspace.[16] The algorithms used in machine learning are made to do a wide range of tasks, including categorization, prediction, and decision-making. Training data is necessary in order to learn the ML algorithms. A model that is regarded as an output of the machine learning algorithm is created following the learning phase. A set of unseen real-time test datasets is then used

to test and validate this model. The overall correctness of the anticipated outcome is then validated by comparing the model's final accuracy with the actual value.[17] [17] A Particle Swarm optimization technique is used to create hybrid model with the support vector machine (SVM) technique.[12] In this work, we have used a survival dataset using machine learning (ML) to analyse the risk factors and prediction in survival of patients with heart failure (HF).[6] The quick development of machine learning techniques and smart tools for heart disease prediction using machine learning models is covered in this summary. An outline of a study aimed at creating a machine learning-based prediction model for cardiac conditions is given in this synopsis. It is anticipated that as the global population increases, so will the disease's mortality rate and number of afflicted individuals. However, early diagnosis and treatment can reduce this fatality rate.[4] The first step is to pre-process the dataset. In the second step, the pre-processed dataset is fed into a number of machine learning algorithms. In the third phase, the models' output is subsequently evaluated using a variety of measures.[4] The main purpose of this study, is to examine the performance indicators such as accuracy, precision, F1 score, and recall that are based on machine learning algorithms. We can quickly determine the evaluation metrics by using the confusion matrix. To get the best outcome, this research uses eleven classifiers and various machine learning approaches, such as cross validation, hyperparameter tuning, and oversampling.[4] Python programming and various supervised machine learning methods, such as Decision Tree, Logistic Regression, Random Forest and KNN are used to examine the dataset's particular variables. The various algorithms like Random Forest (RF), Gradient Boosting (GB), XGBoost, Decision Tree (DT) and Decision Tree Regressor (DTR).[20] Python programming can be implemented using the

Anaconda Jupyter Notebook.[21]Before completing an expensive inquiry, these models might be utilized in preliminary

screening tests to detect high-risk patients.[22], [23]

Background Materials:

We suggested designing and analyzing an improved classifier for heart disease prediction in this paper. We employed various classifiers, evaluated their results, and chose the best one.

A. Data acquisition:

One popular tool for assessing and forecasting heart conditions is the Kaggle heart dataset. It includes a number of patient characteristics that can be used to create machine learning models for the prediction of heart disease. The process of reading data from multiple sources is known as data acquisition. Pandas is an open-source, robust Python library. Data analysis, data manipulation, and data collecting are all done with the Pandas library.

B. Data preprocessing:

The quality of the input data greatly affects the model's evaluation matrices, data preprocessing is a pivotal stage in the creation of machine learning models. Feature selection, feature scaling, missing value treatment, outlier detection, duplication removal, feature correlation, categorical data encoding, and more are included.

Figure 1 Correlation of the features

Figure 2 Chest pain type with Distribution as per target Variable

C. Splitting of Data Set into train and Test:

A critical step in creating machine learning models is dividing a dataset into training and testing sets, as we achieved in our study. Since the model produces dependable performance on anonymous data, it is imperative to make sure it is appropriately trained and assessed.

D. Machine Learning Algorithms:

The following machine learning algorithms are considered:

- Logistic Regression (LR): A linear model used for binary classification [9].
- Decision Tree (DT): A rule-based approach that splits the data based on attribute conditions [10].
- Random Forest (RF): An ensemble learning method that combines multiple decision trees to enhance accuracy [11].
- Support Vector Machine (SVM): A supervised learning algorithm that finds

the optimal hyperplane for classification [12].

- k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN): A distance-based classification algorithm [13].
- **Gradient Boosting (GB):** An ensemble learning technique that builds models sequentially to correct errors of previous models [15].

Performance Metrics:

The models are evaluated based on:

- Accuracy: Measures the proportion of correctly classified instances [16]
- Precision: The ratio of correctly predicted positive observations to total predicted positives [17].
- Recall: The ability of the model to find all positive instances [18].
- F1-score: A harmonic mean of precision and recall [19].

E. Results and Discussion:

Table 1: Comparative Study of individual model

Algorithm	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Logistic Regression	79%	75%	83%	79%
Decision Tree	75%	77%	69%	73%
Random Forest	85%	81%	90%	85%
SVM	80%	76%	86%	81%
k-NN	77%	71%	86%	78%
Gradient Boosting	80%	76%	86%	81%

Figure1: Data Visualisation of Accuracy of each Model

Conclusion:

This paper presents a comparative analysis of machine learning algorithms for heart disease prediction. The study finds that Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, and Neural Networks outperform traditional classifiers in terms of accuracy and other performance metrics. Future research can focus on integrating hybrid models and deep learning techniques to further improve predictive accuracy.

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